

Pest Control and Management

WEEDS

A survey of weeds in transplanted and wet-seeded rice under rainfed and irrigated conditions

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A survey was carried out in Sep 1985 in barangays Sagrada, San Isidro, Pawili, and Takbong of Pili, Camarines Sur, Philippines. Ten wet seeded (pregerminated seed sown on puddled soil) ricefields (six rainfed and four irrigated) and seven transplanted ricefields (three rainfed and four irrigated) were assessed 60–70 d after planting. Percentage weed cover was determined visually.

Severity of weed cover was greater in wet seeded rice and under rainfed conditions. Of the 27 weed species found (see table), 10 were grasses and 6 were sedges. Of the 22 species found in wet seeded rice and 18 found in transplanted rice, 11 were common to both types of culture. More weed species were found under rainfed conditions than irrigated conditions.

Only *Cyperus difformis*, *Echinochloa glabrescens*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, and *Ludwigia octovalvis* were observed in all growing conditions. *Pseudoraphis spinescens*, which has never been reported as a weed of rice in the Philippines, and *F. miliacea* were the major weeds under rainfed conditions. In irrigated transplanted rice, *Monochoria vaginalis* dominated. In irrigated wet seeded rice, the important species were

Percentage weed cover associated with transplanted and wet seeded rice in Pili, Camarines Sur, Philippines.

Weed species	Family	Cover percentage			
		Transplanted rice		Wet seeded rice	
		Rainfed	Irrigated	Rainfed	Irrigated
<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) DC.	Amaranthaceae	–	–	–	11
<i>Commelina diffusa</i> Burm. f.	Commelinaceae	<1	–	–	–
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	Cyperaceae	<1	<1	<1	<1
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	Cyperaceae	4	–	9	<1
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	–	–	<1	–
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	Poaceae	2	–	8	5
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) Beauv. ssp. <i>hispidula</i> (Retz.) Honda	Poaceae	<1	<1	–	–
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i> Munro ex Hook. f.	Poaceae	<1	<1	3	13
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Asteraceae	<1	–	<1	<1
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L. Hassk. var. <i>zippeliana</i> (Bl.) Koster	Asteraceae	1	–	<1	<1
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.) Vahl	Cyperaceae	29	<1	15	15
<i>Isachne globosa</i> (Thunb.) O. K.	Poaceae	<1	<1	–	–
<i>Ischaemum polystachyum</i> Presl	Poaceae	<1	<1	–	–
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.	Poaceae	–	–	1	10
<i>Leersia hexandra</i> Sw.	Poaceae	–	–	<1	–
<i>Lindernia antipoda</i> (L.) Alston	Scrophulariaceae	–	–	<1	<1
<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i> (Jacq.) Raven	Onagraceae	<1	<1	<1	<1
<i>Macropitium lathyroides</i> (L.) Urb.	Papilionaceae	<1	–	<1	–
<i>Marsilea minuta</i> L.	Marsileaceae	<1	–	–	<1
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i> (Burm.f.) Presl	Pontederiaceae	<1	4	–	9
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	Poaceae	–	–	<1	–
<i>Pseudoraphis spinescens</i> (R. Br.) J. Vickery	Poaceae	25	–	55	5
<i>Scirpus grossus</i> L. f.	Cyperaceae	–	–	<1	–
<i>Scirpus supinus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	9	–	–	–
<i>Sphaeranthus africanus</i> L.	Asteraceae	–	–	<1	<1
<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i> Gaertn.	Sphenocleaceae	–	<1	–	<1
<i>Sporobolus diander</i> (Retz.) Beauv.	Poaceae	–	–	<1	–
Total no. of species		17	9	18	16
Species in common (no.)		8		12	
Total cover (%)		72	6	98	70

Alternanthera sessilis, *E. glabrescens*, *F. miliacea*, *Ischaemum rugosum*, and *M. vaginalis*.

Irrigation and transplanting reduced weed cover. □

Control of *Eragrostis japonica* (Thunb.) Trin. in upland rice

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Preemergence herbicides pendimethalin (0.75 and 1.25 kg/ha)

and thiobencarb (1.0 and 1.5 kg/ha) followed by postemergence application of 2,4-D EE and hand weeding were compared with the manually operated, long-handled rotary weeder, 3 hand weedings, and unweeded check in a field experiment in Vertisols of Paramakudi, South India, in 1984–85. *Eragrostis japonica*, the major weed

with a population of 252/m², constituted 90% of the total weed population and caused 86% yield reduction. With pendimethalin at 1.25 kg/ha, it numbered 12 m²; with thiobencarb at 1.50 kg/ha, it was 16 m². Total weed dry matter production at 80 DAS with these treatments was low compared to that with 2 hand